

No data: no policies!

The MINDtheGEPs road to best practices for Gender Equality Plans

VARIOUS MINDtheGEPs EVIDENCE

We need several types of data to be able to capture the various push and pull factors that (de)construct gender (in)equalities in RPO. Why? Because gender is a social structure that is characterized by multiple intersected barriers, requiring multiple intersected actions to be removed. MDG first phase was dedicated to the collection and analysis in 7 public and private RPOs of 4 types of data:

- 1- Quantitative and qualitative data on legislation and policies at the macro level (in the field of R&I and higher education; equal opportunities; employment regulation and labor market; care & work-life balance, including father-friendly policies).
- 2- Quantitative data at the meso-level (53 indicators such as the share of women in governing bodies or in different grades; the share of women applying for or winning competitive funds; the existence of gender measures).
- 3- Quantitative data at the micro-level: a web-survey to research and administrative staff on beliefs around how research performing organizations works and should work.
- 4- Qualitative data at the micro-level: 63 qualitative semi-structured interviews with key-informants (such as rectors and vice rectors, departmental directors; members of competition commissions; the president of Equal Opportunities bodies); 118 qualitative semi-structured interviews with researchers (both early and advanced careers, male and female, representing both STEM and SSH fields).

SOME INSIGHTS FROM INTERVIEWS

- "I have the impression that *women are less ambitious*, I don't know how to say it, I think that this is changing little by little. At the recruiting processes women do not speak openly about their abilities and capacities they prefer to prove it at work first. However, men have more confidence on themselves and place higher demands already at the interviews"
- "We must stop placing *excessive emphasis on the factory, on the product, on workaholic approach*: it is scientifically demonstrable that it harms women more than men. ...
- "No one is forcing women to *take administrative tasks*... I do not know why they end up with those... I cannot disentangle that... whether they are more often offered these tasks or they accept them more readily..."
- "If one has children, she produces less (ironic sigh). And so since you are evaluated for your production, while you have children, others produce so they pass in front of you, and so this is why no one has children ...".

SOME INSIGHTS FROM THE SURVEY

Figure 1. The importance of factors that counts and should count to win a stable position: share declaring "much" or "very much" for early career researchers (left) and stable researchers and professors (right)

FROM GAPS TO GEPS

Why?

A mix of micro, meso, macro factors
 A mix of cultural, structural, institutional factors

How?

FROM MULTIPLE BARRIERS
 TO MULTIPLE ACTIONS

CULTURAL ACTIONS
 STRUCTURAL ACTIONS

With men and women
 With seniors and juniors

